

Retrieval of Column Water Vapor Amount from MODIS Channels Near 1 μm

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INTRODUCTION

The Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) [1] [2] is a major facility instrument for the NASA Earth Observing System (EOS) to be launched in the summer of 1998. MODIS has 36 channels located in the spectral region between 0.41 and 14.3 μm . Most of these channels have heritage traceable to previous satellite instruments, such as NOAA AVHRR, HIRS, CZCS, and Landsat TM. However, several channels in the near-IR solar spectral region have been selected for the MODIS instrument based on our observations from hyperspectral imaging data acquired with the NASA JPL Airborne Visible/Infrared Imaging Spectrometer (AVIRIS) [3] from an ER-2 aircraft at 20 km. Several near-IR channels located within and around the 0.94- μm water vapor absorption region are selected for remote sensing of integrated atmospheric water vapor over land. In this paper, we describe the physical principles of remote sensing column atmospheric water vapor using near-IR channels within and around the 0.94- μm water vapor band from MODIS measurements.

WATER VAPOR REMOTE SENSING

Historically, remote sensing of water vapor profiles from space was made using IR emission channels. The results depended in part on the initial guess for the temperature and moisture profiles used in the inversion [4]. Column water vapor amounts over the ocean were retrieved from IR emission channels in the 11 - 13 μm spectral region using "split window" techniques [5] and from microwave emission measurements. The "split window" techniques also work well

over land areas covered by green vegetation. When the apparent surface temperature, which is the product of surface emissivity and skin temperature, is about equal to the average temperature of the boundary layer, where most of the water vapor usually resides, infrared and microwave remote sensing will not be sensitive to the boundary layer water vapor.

MODIS has implemented near-IR channels within and around the 0.94- μm water vapor band for remote sensing of column water vapor amounts over the globe from a satellite platform. Five near-IR channels are useful for remote sensing of water vapor. The positions and widths of these channels are given in Table 1 and illustrated in Figure 1. Two atmospheric water vapor transmittance spectra for the Tropical and Sub-Arctic Winter Models in LOWTRAN7 [6] with a solar zenith angle of 45 degrees and a nadir-looking geometry are also shown in Figure 1. The channels at 0.865 and 1.24 μm are non-absorption channels present on MODIS for remote sensing of vegetation and clouds. The channels at 0.935, 0.940, and 0.905 μm are water vapor absorption channels with decreasing absorption coefficients. The strong absorption channel at 0.935 μm is most useful for dry conditions, while the weak absorption channel at 0.905 μm is most useful for very humid conditions, or low solar elevation [7]. Techniques employing ratios of water vapor absorbing channels at 0.905, 0.936, and 0.940 μm with atmospheric window channels at 0.865 and 1.24 μm are used in our retrieval algorithm. The ratios remove partially the effects of variation of surface reflectance with wavelengths and results in the atmospheric water vapor transmittances. A look-up table containing theoretically calculated water vapor transmittances is generated using the LOWTRAN7 code. The column water vapor amounts are derived by comparing the "measured"

Table 1: Positions and widths of five MODIS near-IR channels used in water vapor retrievals.

MODIS Channel #	Position (μm)	Width (μm)
2	0.865	0.040
5	1.240	0.020
17	0.905	0.030
18	0.936	0.010
19	0.940	0.050

Fig. 1. Positions and widths of five MODIS near-IR channels marked in thick horizontal bars, and 2-way atmospheric water vapor transmittance spectra for Tropical and Sub-Arctic Winter Models in LOWTRAN7 (Kneizys et al., 1988) with a solar zenith angle of 45 degrees and a nadir-looking geometry.

transmittances with "simulated" transmittances using a look-up table procedure.

CORRECTION OF AEROSOL EFFECTS

Under very hazy conditions, the 0.94- μm water vapor channels may not see the absorption by water vapor in the bottom layer of the atmosphere. The transmittance model assumed in our retrievals will introduce errors in the derived water vapor values from MODIS data. The effect of haze on remote sensing of water vapor depends on the amount of haze and the magnitude of the surface reflectances. Under typical atmospheric conditions with visibilities of 20 km or greater, the aerosol effects on water vapor retrievals are not significant. Our sensitivity studies have shown that aerosol effects on water vapor retrievals are not negligible for dark surfaces (reflectance less than 0.1 near 1 μm) and for bright surfaces (reflectance greater than 0.5) when the aerosol optical depth at 0.55 μm is greater than 0.5. A scheme for correcting aerosol effects has been developed and implemented in our

MODIS near-IR water vapor algorithm. The scheme consists of three steps: (1) using a look-up table procedure to derive an initial column water vapor amount value from the transmittances based on theoretical atmospheric gaseous transmittance calculations, (2) computing a correction factor in the case of dark surfaces (reflectance less than 0.1 near 1 μm) and for bright surfaces (reflectance greater than 0.5) when the aerosol optical depth at 0.55 μm is greater than 0.5 using looking up tables generated through radiative transfer calculations in which rural and tropospheric aerosols are included, and (3) applying the correction factor to the water vapor amount value derived in step (1).

SUMMARY

The MODIS instrument has implemented near-IR channels for remote sensing water vapor from space. After the launching of the MODIS instrument in the summer of 1998, we expect that our ability in satellite remote sensing of integrated atmospheric water vapor will be improved dramatically.

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